

- develop students' communication and observation skills;
- achieve students' fluency in using language units in various situations;
- achieve students' instilling such skills as selection, study and use.

Thus, the foundations of using a foreign language as a means of communication are laid from the junior classes. During this period, if they explain their thoughts in an unfamiliar situation, read and understand any simple text, participate in role-playing games, they can easily continue this work in senior classes. At this stage, students must communicate using simple speech designations in accordance with their interests, know the names of objects that they encounter in everyday life, distinguish and pronounce various sounds of the foreign language being studied compared to their native language, and learn the skills of explaining their content by reading short texts. During this period, they simultaneously develop basic writing skills.

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ЕФЕКТИВНІ СПОСОБИ І МЕТОДИ НАВЧАННЯ АНГЛІЙСЬКОЇ МОВИ В ПОЧАТКОВИХ КЛАСАХ

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У зв'язку з тим, що освіта Азербайджану спрямована на вихід у світовий освітній простір, питанням навчання іноземних мов, особливо оновленню цілей, змісту, принципів, засобів та методів приділяється значна увага. З цієї точки зору актуальним завданням вважається дослідження та застосування нової моделі навчання та технологій викладання іноземної мови як соціально розвивається. В умовах, коли світ переживає потужний процес глобалізації та інтеграції, завдання освіти полягає не лише у підготовці здібної молоді, а й у формуванні з неї осіб, які відповідають вимогам часу.

На етапі розвитку сучасного суспільства модернізація освіти в Азербайджані пов'язана із застосуванням інноваційних процесів в організації іноземної мови. Сьогодні в центрі уваги стоїть учень, його особистість та унікальний внутрішній світ. В останні роки на уроках англійської початкових класів застосовуються нові технології навчання. Це також навчання нових форм і методів, тобто нового підходу до процесу навчання.

Таким чином, основною метою навчання англійської мови у початкових класах є формування комунікативної культури школяра, розвиток особистості та практичне оволодіння іноземною мовою. Його основне завдання – розвиток основ комунікативних та розвиваючих компетенцій учнів. Проте це завдання передбачає формування в учнів як практичних навичок, а й певних якостей особистості: виховання учнів товариськими, самостійними, незалежними мислителями, здатних ухвалювати рішення, схильних до встановлення комунікативних відносин із друзями. Поняття принципу активності передбачає таку діяльність, яка характеризує високий рівень мотивації, трансформацію знань та умінь у затребуваність, орієнтованість на результат та відповідність соціальним нормам. Аналізуються прийоми та форми, спрямовані на формування високої мотиваційної складової у навчальному процесі.

Ключові слова: початкові класи, навчання іноземної мови, комунікативна компетентність, мотивація, навчання, учні.

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ACTIVE POSITION AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN PUPILS ACQUIRING AN ACTIVE CIVIC STANCE

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In the context of an active civic position, senior school students are constantly engaged in self-improvement, self-education and self-development, trying to demonstrate their abilities and skills. The formation of an active civic position includes enriching the spiritual world of schoolchildren, conducting targeted, systematic and continuous work to promote its high social goals and morals, as well as to improve political and moral culture. An active civic position is a clear awareness of public civic duty, moral and legal responsibility, its obligations to society, the development of patriotism, a sense of national pride, knowledge of one's rights and obligations, as well as compliance with the requirements of the law. When forming a civic position, three issues should be in the center of attention. Firstly, high school students should have accurate knowledge and information about the world, society and themselves. This knowledge and information are necessary for a better understanding of the connections and dependencies between behavioral norms and people's actions. Secondly, in the process of continuous self-realization, socially useful activity of the student, the assimilation of forms of social relations is of great importance. Thirdly, students acquire experience and culture of communication, which facilitates and improves their relationships and interactions with peers and other people. The work on forming an active civic position should be started from a young age. The basis of this position is the worldview, moral and spiritual faith of the individual and his attitude to public duty. The following are indicators of an active civic position: purposeful, systematic and conscious activity of schoolchildren, including students in grades X-XI; activity and responsibility in a particular activity; compliance of the activities and social activity of senior schoolchildren with the requirements of the type of activity and living conditions in society; real activity of the individual and way of life.

The formation of a civic position implies a system of education and training of students, which manifests itself as an important condition for the formation of a moral civic position of an individual. An active civic position is a clear awareness of public civic duty, moral and legal responsibility, its obligations to society, the education of patriotism, a sense of national pride, knowledge of one's rights and obligations, as well as compliance with the requirements of the law. A citizen of Azerbaijan is a historical achievement of the independent and sovereign Republic of Azerbaijan.

Key words: formation of active civic position, high school students, teachers, personality development, learning process.

A citizen of Azerbaijan is a historical achievement of the independent and sovereign Republic of Azerbaijan. The concept of «citizenship» is closely related to the concepts of «citizen» and «civil law». The formation of an active civic position depends on how well the process of education and upbringing in comprehensive schools is organized. Naturally, it is advisable to organize this work in a scientific form. Formation of an active civic position is one of the important tasks of moral education. As the Republic of Azerbaijan develops and strengthens, takes its rightful place among the countries of the world, its material and spiritual wealth is enriched, the need for comprehensive and harmonious development of its citizens grows. At present, the objective need for comprehensive and harmonious development of the individual, the citizen is in the center of attention of the material and technical base of the country, improvement of interpersonal relations, strengthening and development of the way of life and manifestation of the laws of education of a new type of personality. The ability to understand the essence of moral problems from the point of view of the criteria of active citizenship consists of identifying certain duties for oneself. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure a high level of morality for everyone, for schoolchildren, including senior schoolchildren. The fact is that this or that behavior that contradicts society is the result of deviation from the generally accepted norms of society, legal and ethical norms. Our morality and ethics are becoming more meaningful and rich. Citizenship, being a moral position of senior pupils, is reflected in their sense of duty and responsibility to the state, family, mosque, profession they receive, to the collective of which they are a member. Being a very valuable example of consciousness and behavior of a schoolchild, citizenship has a direct impact on his political activity, ensures the fulfillment of civic duties and ultimately becomes the basis of the social and political culture of senior pupils. It is important to periodically check how the active civic position of students is formed. For this purpose, monitoring and assessment, pedagogical examination, pedagogical and psychological diagnostics can be used.

An active civic position can be considered as a system of views of a student on life, people, the activities of peers and the nature of this activity. A civic position reflects the attitude of an individual to society, activities, people and himself. Citizenship is considered in any country, including the Republic of Azerbaijan, as a psychological situation with the legal status of a person, as well as with his or her position in socio-political relations. Educational and upbringing work carried out in the field of formation of a civic position prevents deviant behavior of schoolchildren, promotes their involvement in socially useful activities, promotes the development of moral and legal culture and civic activity. Love for the homeland, readiness to sacrifice oneself for the sake of the homeland, respect for the laws of the country, ethical standards, respect for the native language, historical heritage, study of culture, customs and traditions, spiritual values of the people are of great importance in terms of mastering an active civic position. The formation of a civic position implies a system of education and training of students, which manifests itself as an important condition for the formation of a moral civic position of an individual.

An active civic position means that people, including educated people, clearly understand their duty of public citizenship, moral and legal responsibility, the duties imposed on them by society, are patriots, have a

sense of national honor and national pride, take good care of the material and spiritual wealth of their native country, and also know their rights and responsibilities.

The position of an active citizen can be considered as a system of views of a schoolchild on life, the activities of people, peers and the nature of this activity. The fact is that a person cannot rise to the level of an active civic position without having certain, or rather, necessary convictions, conscious responsibility and a sense of duty. All this shows that it is necessary to clearly understand the ways and means of forming a personality, including an educated one, and to organize this work in order to be able to live and act in a civil society, approaching life with new values.

Civic consciousness is manifested not only in respect for one's own and others' rights and obligations, the law and legality, but also in indifference to mass troubles, disasters and suffering. They must be seen, felt, interested in and reacted to. A true citizen must be sensitive to the fate of others, be kind, provide selfless assistance, not be indifferent to social cataclysms, be intolerant of exploitation by someone else, crimes against society, abuse of power and position. Therefore, in the conditions of the formation of civil society and the rule of law, the main task of general education institutions, as well as other types of schools, should be the education of democratic citizens. These people should have the opportunity to implement innovations, manage their lives and activities, ensure their financial well-being with decent work, and also actively and closely participate in the life of society.

Formation of an active civic position in schoolchildren, including senior pupils, occupies an important place in the educational system of a comprehensive school. This is not accidental. The position of active citizenship helps students to get out of difficult situations, make independent decisions, take responsibility by integrating the student's beliefs, ideal-spiritual and moral thinking and qualities, loyalty to the Motherland, readiness to defend their country.

Student self-government bodies also have important responsibilities for developing an active civic position in senior pupils. Self-government bodies are created in the educational institution for both classes and the entire school. Close participation in self-government activities develops in senior pupils the skills of behavior, speech, correct behavior and communication necessary for an active civic position.

The signs of a citizen's position are deep respect for their historical past, present and future, our statehood, a sense of pride in the material and spiritual wealth of our country. Every person, including students, who wants to live in a legal state, a democratic country and wants to be the master of their life, never remains outside the life of society, they assert their civic position. This position, first of all, turns the fulfillment of civic duty into a demand. The position of citizenship is also expressed in the desire to discuss and resolve common issues and problems, and this aspect occupies a leading place in the activities of student self-government bodies.

The formation of an active civic position requires that, when preparing the younger generation for independent life, we must first of all think about appropriate ways to introduce them to the socio-political and moral values of society.

For the effective formation of a civic position, it is necessary to teach high school students civic responsibility and sacred duty to the Motherland. Civil responsibility includes the following aspects: conscious and positive attitude of the student to his rights and obligations; the internal need to coordinate these rights and obligations with the requirements of society. Enmity and opposition to immoral actions, mutual assistance, the ability to mobilize oneself and others to fight against antisocial manifestations, etc. d. appear as objective indicators of responsibility.

Civic responsibility is inextricably linked with the sense of civic duty and finds its manifestation in it.

Formation of an active civic position presupposes development of social activity, civic consciousness and civic qualities as a component of an active civic position of the personality of high school students. This is manifested in the civic behavior of high school students.

Manifestation of an active civic position is a necessary condition for maturity and improvement of the civic position of high school students. In other words, understanding the importance of taking responsibility for the fate of one's country, feeling concern for its future, putting public interest above personal interest, asking for help if the situation requires it, all this is extremely important in forming an active civic position.

The formation of an active civic position of high school students lies in the fact that the formed civic position of teachers influences the level of civic position of high school students, the motivation of members of the teaching staff, teachers to interact with students allows them to form a position of citizenship.

The main components of an active civic position include the following:

1. Civic qualities (feeling of love for one's parents who gave him life, for one's family in which he grew up; strong and deep attachment to one's homeland, feelings of love for one's native land, homeland;

2. Know one's rights and obligations defined by the Constitution and fulfill them, being aware of one's obligations;
3. Take responsibility for one's actions and deeds, do not allow any negative actions;
4. Independence, initiative;
5. Civic consciousness etc.

The thesis states that an active position is indeed an important factor in students acquiring an active civic position. The effectiveness of educating senior students in active citizenship is determined by the following conditions:

- There is a demand for civic position among high school students.
- Teachers themselves have a high level of civic consciousness.
- The educational process and extracurricular activities create the necessary opportunities in terms of developing the civic position of students.
- Motivating teachers to interact and be active in the context of developing and forming an active civic position among high school students.

From the above it follows that we need to have a clear understanding of the ways and means of forming the personality, including students, to organize this work, to be able to live and work in a civil society with new values and views.

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СОЦІАЛЬНА ТВОРЧІСТЬ ЯК ВАЖЛИВИЙ ЧИННИК НАБУТТЯ УЧНЯМИ АКТИВНОЇ ГРОМАДЯНСЬКОЇ ПОЗИЦІЇ

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Активна громадянська позиція – це чітке усвідомлення людиною суспільного громадянського обов'язку, моральної та юридичної відповідальності, її зобов'язань перед суспільством, виховання патріотизму, почуття національної гордості, знання своїх прав та обов'язків, а також дотримання вимог законів. При формуванні громадянської позиції у центрі уваги мають стояти три питання. По-перше, старшокласники повинні мати конкретні знання та інформацію про світ, суспільство та про себе. Ці знання та інформація необхідні для кращого розуміння зв'язків та залежностей між поведінковими нормами та діями людей. По-друге, у процесі безперервної самореалізації, суспільно-корисної діяльності учня, важливе значення має засвоєння форм суспільних відносин. По-третє, учні набувають досвіду та культури спілкування, що полегшує і покращує їхнє взаємовідносини та взаємодію з однолітками та іншими людьми. До роботи з формування активної громадянської позиції необхідно приступити з молодшого віку. Основу цієї позиції становить світогляд, морально-духовна віра особистості та її ставлення до суспільного обов'язку. Аналізуються шляхи та засоби формування цієї позиції учнів на прикладі їх соціокультурної діяльності.

Ключові слова: формування активної громадянської позиції, учні старших класів, вчителі, розвиток особистості, процес навчання.

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